

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

D2.5. Synthesised statement of requirement report for EuroGO-SHIP

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Work Package	WP2: Concept Development Through Co-design
Lead Partner	CNR
Lead Author (Org)	Katrin Schroeder (CNR)
Contributing Author(s)	Marta Álvarez (CSIC), Carolina Cantoni (CNR ISMAR), Fiona Carse (MET-UK), Caroline Cusack (MI), Yvonne L. Firing (NOC), Emil Jeansson (NORCE), Johannes Karstensen (GEOMAR), Martin Kramp (OCEAN OPS), Magali Krieger (OCEAN OPS), Siv K. Lauvset (NORCE), Pascale Lherminier (IFREMER), Elaine McDonagh (NORCE), Are Olsen (UiB), Kristin Richter (NORCE), Emmanuel Salmon (ICOS-RI), Elena Saltikoff (ICOS-RI), Richard Sanders (NORCE), Tim Smyth (PML), Tobias Steinhoff (GEOMAR), Dan Vasiliu (GeoEcoMar), Antón Velo (CSIC), Ryan Weber (NORCE), Malcolm Woodward (PML)
Reviewers	Ryan Weber (NORCE)
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1. Executive Summary

The EuroGO-SHIP project is a collaborative initiative aimed at enhancing the coordination and implementation of ship-based hydrographic data collection across Europe, ensuring high-quality data collection, quality assurance, and management — not only on dedicated hydrographic cruises but also on other research and operational cruises, such as fisheries surveys, where hydrographic data are collected. The project also emphasizes training, mentoring, and knowledge-sharing to improve analytical quality both in the lab and at sea.

This report synthesizes the needs and requirements for the potential establishment of a future EuroGO-SHIP Research Infrastructure (RI). It emphasizes critical aspects to be considered in the design of a future EuroGO-SHIP RI, such as data flow, sample collection, analyses, quality control, community engagement, training, knowledge transfer, developing and sharing best practices, and ensuring administrative and governance structures. The design elements include standardizing practices in hydrographic research, improving data quality and data access, and facilitating the effective use of oceanographic data to support scientific research and policy-making related to marine environments.

The report outlines the methodologies and tools proposed for data acquisition, curation, and quality control, which are envisioned to be the cornerstone of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. It also highlights best practices and strategies for community engagement, ensuring that the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders are considered in the project's implementation. Building on the work carried out in key deliverables of the project—including reports on shared facilities (D2.2, D3.2), data curation and quality control (D2.3, D2.4), best practices (D3.1, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5), and stakeholder consultations (D4.1–D4.4)—this synthesis provides a comprehensive foundation for shaping the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. The complete list of deliverables considered here is provided in Appendix 1.

2. Introduction

2.1. Overview

The EuroGO-SHIP (European Global Ocean Ship-based Hydrographic Investigations Program) is an infrastructure concept design project that includes analysis of the current practices of nations' shipbased hydrographic data collection, data quality control, and data storage to derive recommendations for pan-European collaboration in order to enhance the quality and accessibility of oceanographic data across Europe. Potential benefits of a pan-European collaboration, and the contribution to the European Research Area (ERA) include improved understanding of ocean dynamics and of changes in hydrographic structures in oceanic and regional sea regions of European interest, which in turn provide improved characterization of climate change impacts on European Seas, which will, for example, facilitate sustainable management of marine resources. The project emphasizes collaboration among various stakeholders, including research institutions, governmental agencies, and the private sector, to ensure comprehensive data collection and sharing.

2.2. Objectives of the report

The primary objective of this report is to synthesize the requirements for a future EuroGO-SHIP RI, providing a clear roadmap for its implementation. A first version of a value chain that schematizes the conceptual framework of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI is shown in Figure 1, illustrating how the aim is to improve *in-situ* observations and data quality control while providing valuable information to both intermediate (e.g. scientists) and end users (e.g. policy makers). The roadmap for its implementation, described in this report, includes outlining the necessary data management practices, quality control measures, and community engagement strategies essential for the success of the project, as well as providing guidance for its transition into a fully operational RI.

The contents of this deliverable reflect the outcomes of an online “Synthesis Workshop for the Statement of Requirements” (Milestone MS19), held on 12th December 2024. The workshop, attended by key project partners, aimed to review and consolidate findings from previous deliverables (listed in Annex 1), covering aspects such as shared facilities, data curation, quality control, best practices, and consultation outcomes. Discussions were structured around a series of presentations and interactive sessions, ensuring broad input from the community.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI illustrating the integration of *in-situ* observations, data quality control, and the flow of information to promote scientific research and inform policy-making.

Following this, a focused drafting group meeting was held in Bergen from 14th–16th January 2025, where a smaller group of project partners refined the structure of D2.5 and defined its key messages. This follow-up session ensured that the synthesis report effectively integrates

the collective insights gathered throughout the project, forming a comprehensive foundation for the future EuroGO-SHIP RI.

3. Data flow/Data Life Cycle Management

3.1. Overview

A data flow mapping exercise carried out during the EuroGO-SHIP project (see D2.3 “Report of data curation recommendations including gap analysis”) has provided valuable insights into the current state of data management within the oceanographic community. While European data aggregators such as EMODnet, Coriolis, and SeaDataNet, as well as global data centers like SEANOE and PANGAEA, have established and recommended standards, challenges remain in their consistent implementation and adoption. One of the key findings was the difficulty in effectively tracking data, primarily due to inconsistencies in the use of existing standards and the absence of a widely adopted lifecycle identifier—specifically, a consistent cruise ID. This lack of standardization complicates the ability to trace data from collection through to its final use, hindering integration and usability. Additionally, challenges arose in querying and locating specific datasets, as the relevant metadata and formats were sometimes unclear or inconsistent (e.g. ADCP data formats in SeaDataNet).

Additionally, the exercise uncovered inconsistencies in data management practices across different countries (see also D4.3 “Report on the results of consultations government ministries and funding agencies”). The varied use of identifiers not only creates challenges in data sharing but also leads to discrepancies in data quality and accessibility. These inconsistencies can impede collaborative research efforts and diminish the overall reliability of oceanographic data. Addressing these challenges is crucial for establishing a more streamlined and efficient data management framework, which is essential for advancing scientific research and fostering international cooperation within the hydrographic community. This section provides a comprehensive examination of the processes involved in the acquisition, curation, and quality control of data, which are envisioned to be the cornerstone of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. It recalls the methodologies and tools proposed for data collection, the practices for managing and storing data, and the rigorous quality control measures that will be implemented to ensure data integrity and reliability.

The section is structured to cover the following key areas:

- Hydrographic cruise planning and execution: This section details the planning and execution of hydrographic cruises, including the logistical considerations, coordination with research vessels, and the protocols followed to ensure successful data collection missions. For more detailed information, refer to D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities”.
- Data acquisition: This section is about the methods and tools used to gather data, as well as the various sources from which data is obtained. For more detailed information, refer to D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities”.

- Data curation: Here, we explore the practices and solutions for managing and storing data. Detailed recommendations can be found in D2.3 “Report of data curation recommendations including gap analysis”.
- Primary Quality Control (QC1): This section focuses on the initial validation and error detection techniques applied to raw data. It also discusses the metadata requirements. For a framework on uncertainty estimates, see D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities” and M11 “M11, Software for Primary quality control of observational data”
- Secondary Quality Control (QC2): This section covers the framework for uncertainty estimates. It highlights the importance of secondary QC in refining data quality and providing reliable datasets for scientific research. Further details are available in D2.4 “Report on framework for uncertainty estimates as part of secondary quality control”.
- Maintenance of QC tools: The final section emphasizes the need for regular maintenance and updates of QC tools to keep pace with evolving standards and technological advancements.

3.2. Hydrographic cruise planning and execution

Hydrographic cruises are the backbone of data collection efforts which will be enhanced by a future EuroGO-SHIP RI. Effective planning and execution of these cruises are essential to ensure the successful acquisition of high-quality data.

Planning a hydrographic cruise involves detailed logistical arrangements, including securing funding and ensuring that all necessary equipment, supplies, permissions and personnel are available and that the cruise timeline aligns with scientific objectives and environmental conditions. The PI needs to coordinate with research vessel operators to ensure that the vessel is equipped with the necessary instruments and that the crew is trained and prepared for the specific requirements of the hydrographic survey, as well as with co-investigators to ensure user-supplied equipment (e.g. laboratory analysis equipment) and trained personnel are available. This coordination includes pre-cruise meetings to discuss objectives, methodologies, safety protocols and to set in place any required diplomatic clearances to work in national waters of other states. Finally, establishing standardized protocols for data collection, sample handling and storage, use of certified reference materials and instrument calibration is vital to ensure consistency and reliability across different cruises. These protocols are developed in consultation with experts and are based on best practices in the field, but in practice may differ according to ship and country.

During the cruise, instruments such as CTD sensors, rosettes with Niskin bottles, and ADCPs are deployed according to the established protocols. Careful attention is paid to the calibration and maintenance of these instruments to ensure accurate data collection. Seawater samples are collected using Niskin bottles mounted on a rosette sampler. These samples are carefully handled and preserved for subsequent analysis in the laboratory on the ship, or are stored according to accepted protocols for later analysis back on land. Detailed records are kept to track the location, depth, and conditions of each sample. Real-time logging and monitoring is used to track the performance of instruments and the quality of the data

being collected to allow for immediate troubleshooting and adjustments if any issues arise during the cruise.

3.3. Data acquisition

Data acquisition is a critical phase in the data value chain within the Future EuroGO-SHIP RI, where it is ensured that high-quality data is collected to support scientific research and analysis. This section briefly reviews the methods and tools used for data collection in hydrography.

Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs¹, see Figure 2) are those parameters that provide a comprehensive understanding of ocean dynamics and health. These variables are identified by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and are essential for delivering ocean forecasts, climate projections, and assessments. The EuroGO-SHIP project recognizes the importance of EOVs in guiding its research efforts and ensuring that data collected is relevant and impactful. EOVs may depend on one or more observed quantities or parameters (referred to as “supporting variables” in the GOOS EO specification sheet), and the reproducible uncertainties of these parameters. EOVs include ocean current, temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, carbonate system parameters, inorganic nutrients, and transient tracers. The EOVs in turn include derived variables such as surface ocean stress, surface/subsurface ocean currents, ocean heat uptake, which among others are vital for monitoring oceanographic changes and assessing the impacts of climate change. For any EO, the aspect of reproducible uncertainties goes hand in hand with providing (and archiving) the specific Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that outline the data quality approaches.

3.3.1. Methods and tools

The future EuroGO-SHIP RI members will employ specific, codified methods and tools to acquire data, ensuring accuracy and consistency across different datasets. For each method there will be an associated expert group (see section 4.4 of this report), specific recommendations and training activities concerning best practices and standard operating procedures. Key methods and tools include:

- Conductivity-Temperature-Depth (CTD) sensors: These sensors are used to measure the conductivity, temperature, and depth (pressure) of seawater, and may be accompanied by sensors for other parameters such as dissolved oxygen and several optical parameters. CTD casts are performed using a rosette sampler equipped with Niskin bottles, which collect seawater samples at various depths.
- Niskin bottles on a rosette sampler: Niskin bottles are used to collect discrete seawater samples at different depths during CTD casts. These samples are then analyzed for various chemical and biological parameters, providing detailed information about the water column (see Figure 2).

¹ <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>
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- Vessel-Mounted Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (VMADCP): These instruments are mounted on research vessels to measure the speed and direction of water currents throughout the water column. ADCPs provide continuous current profiles as the vessel moves. Here, the development of standardized vocabulary and tools is essential for enhancing data interoperability and usability.
- Lowered Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (LADCPs): LADCPs are mounted on the CTD frame and deployed on CTD casts to derive a current velocity profile at each station, from the surface to the seafloor.
- Other underway instruments, that can be set up to transmit data to shore in real time.

Although it is not the “core business” of hydrography, ongoing efforts to enhance the availability of real-time data are gaining momentum within the oceanographic community (e.g. providing valuable data to help improve ocean and weather forecasting). A particular EuroGO-SHIP focus was on increasing the number of countries actively transmitting near real time data (e.g. underway data and CTD profiles; see D4.4 “Report summarising the results of consultations with end users”). A future EuroGO-SHIP RI would facilitate this process, providing valuable contributions to ocean and weather forecasts and supporting the development of reliable ocean digital twins.

Figure 2: Schematic of EOVs (left) and a CTD/rosette deployment from a Research Vessel at a hydrographic station (right).

3.4. Data curation

Data curation will be a vital process within the future EuroGO-SHIP RI, ensuring that collected data is properly managed, stored, quality controlled and validated to maintain its integrity and usability. This section outlines the practices and solutions for data management, storage, and quality control that we envisage to be standardized within the future EuroGO-SHIP RI.

3.4.1. Data management practices

Effective data management practices are essential for maintaining the quality and accessibility of data, and ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability). For instance, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will

implement the following practices to ensure data and metadata are managed according to FAIR principles:

- Standardized metadata and data formats: Metadata will be standardized at the point of collection to ensure consistency, while data—initially collected in different formats depending on instrumentation—will be converted into standardized formats before entering data centers.
- Data documentation: All data collection methods, processing steps, and metadata will be fully documented to provide context and ensure reproducibility.
- Version control: A version control system will be implemented to track changes and updates to datasets, ensuring that the most current and accurate data is available.
- Data access and sharing: Defined protocols will be established to regulate data access and sharing, supporting interoperability and reusability.

Box 1: Overview of data curation recommendations (from D2.3 “Report of data curation recommendations including gap analysis”)

Motivation and background:

- The need for a European infrastructure for hydrography stems from experiences with international structures like International GO-SHIP and ICES.
- Valuable ocean observation data is gathered during research cruises, including physical, chemical, and biological properties.

Current challenges:

- Delayed-mode data submission procedures and formats from the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) are outdated and not always applicable.
- Advancements in technology and changes in national data policies have led to fragmented data flows and inconsistent data availability.
- Data producers are often unaware of how and where their data is available internationally, leading to gaps and difficulties in data tracking.

Methodology:

- Implementation of a persistent and full lifecycle Cruise-ID scheme by OceanOPS.
- Input from key stakeholders in hydrographic data production and management.
- Visualization of the draft (meta-) data landscape and a global survey to identify national data best practices.
- Recommendations for data formats for CTD and bottle data, and analysis of delayed-mode data availability at different repositories.

Key findings:

- Differences in participation in research cruise data submission across nations.
- Difficulties in attributing datasets to specific research cruises and identifying the 'best' or 'final' version of a dataset.
- Progress in VMADCP data curation and harmonized netCDF data format recommendations.
- Increased availability of near real-time CTD data to forecasting centres.

Recommendations:

- Adoption of a netCDF format containing data, metadata, and quality control (QC) flags.
- Use of interoperable vocabularies and persistent identifiers (DOI, PID) for datasets and related entities.
- Implementation of a full lifecycle Cruise-ID allocated by OceanOPS to facilitate FAIR data and metadata flows.
- Automated exchange of metadata between cruise planning facilities and OceanOPS.

3.4.2. Data storage solutions

The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will not create new data repositories but will provide comprehensive guidelines on where to submit datasets within existing repositories, along with clear recommendations on the required metadata to ensure consistency, interoperability, and compliance with FAIR principles.

This approach will ensure that data is stored in well-established, reliable repositories while maintaining consistency and accessibility. These storage solutions might include:

- National Oceanographic Data Centers (NODCs): submission to NODCs is typically required by the country funding hydrographic activities and may follow different procedures across Europe. These centres manage data collected by national and international programs.
- SeaDataNet: this infrastructure connects European NODCs and other marine data centres, facilitating the management and sharing of marine and oceanographic data, regardless of whether the data originates from European waters or from European research efforts conducted globally.
- Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS): CMEMS offers a centralized platform for the submission of marine data, including real-time and delayed-mode datasets.
- European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet): EMODnet is another key repository for European marine data. It provides access to a wide range of marine data and supports data sharing and integration across Europe.
- SEANOE (SEA scientific Open data Edition) is an open scientific data repository in the marine sciences field. Currently operated by the SISMER² marine data center within the ODATIS³ Ocean Cluster framework and funded by Ifremer. EMODnet Ingestion network marine data centers will be informed of datasets published in SEANOE thanks to automatic duplication system. Each dataset published on SEANOE will get a unique DOI which allow it to be published and cited in the most reliable and sustainable way.
- Global Data Assembly Centers (GDACs): For international data sharing, GDACs such as the GO-SHIP GDAC (CCHDO) play a key role in facilitating global access to high-quality oceanographic data. Other major data repositories, such as the National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI), also serve as important archives for oceanographic datasets.

Ideally, a streamlined data flow would be established to minimize the need for multiple submissions by Principal Investigators (PIs), potentially tasking NODCs with forwarding data to GDACs to ensure compliance with both national and international data policies. In an ideal world, PIs would only need to update the dataset associated with a persistent identifier (DOI or PID), rather than submitting data to multiple data centers. This practice enhances traceability, citation, and long-term data management while aligning with FAIR data principles.

² <https://data.ifremer.fr/SISMER>

³ <https://www.odatis-ocean.fr/>

Concerning NODCs, understanding the flow of data through them is essential for effective data curation. Therefore, a future EuroGO-SHIP RI will promote a mapping exercise to:

- Identify data pathways: Map the pathways through which data flows from collection to storage at NODCs, identifying key points of data transfer and processing.
- Assess data handling practices: Evaluate the data handling practices at the different NODCs to ensure that they align with EGS RI standards and best practices.
- Optimize data integration: Develop strategies to optimize data integration and interoperability between different NODCs, facilitating seamless data sharing and collaboration.

3.4.3. Primary Quality Control (QC1)

Primary quality control (QC1) ensures the highest quality of data collected at each station by applying standardized validation procedures during and immediately after acquisition. This step helps identify and correct errors early, ensuring data integrity at the source.

QC1 is the first step in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of collected data (see D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities”). The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will create guidelines, software tools (see M11 “Software for Primary quality control of observational data”) and training activities to make sure for all European hydrographic activities the following primary QC measures are implemented:

INITIAL DATA VALIDATION	Real-time issue monitoring	Utilize real-time monitoring systems to validate data as it is collected, identifying and addressing any issues immediately
	Calibration checks	Perform regular calibration checks on instruments to ensure that they are functioning correctly and providing accurate measurements
ERROR DETECTION TECHNIQUES	Automated error detection	Implement automated error detection algorithms to identify anomalies and inconsistencies in the data. Flag the data with standard quality labels to track the QC1 procedures
	Manual review	Conduct manual reviews of data to catch errors that automated systems may miss
METADATA REQUIREMENTS	Comprehensive metadata	Ensure that all datasets are accompanied by comprehensive metadata, including information on data collection methods, processing steps, and quality control measures
	Standardized metadata formats	Use standardized metadata formats to facilitate easy sharing and integration of data across different platforms and systems

3.4.4. Secondary Quality Control (QC2) as a framework for uncertainty estimates

Secondary quality control (QC2) focuses on harmonizing data across multiple cruises, ensuring that datasets can be reliably merged to develop comprehensive data products. This step includes cross-cruise comparisons, bias corrections, and uncertainty assessments to enhance the consistency and usability of integrated datasets. QC2 builds on QC1 by applying additional verification methods to ensure consistency across datasets from multiple cruises. While uncertainty estimates are considered at both QC1 and QC2 stages, QC2 focuses on **EuroGO-SHIP** | D2.5. Synthesised statement of requirement report for EuroGO-SHIP

harmonizing data across cruises and refining uncertainty assessments in the context of integrated data products. More details can be found in the D2.4 “Report on framework for uncertainty estimates as part of secondary quality control”. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will develop guidelines and organize training activities to ensure that data collected across European hydrographic activities can undergo QC2 at the RI level. This process will focus on comparing and harmonizing datasets from multiple cruises, ensuring that high-quality data products integrate consistent and reliable information:

ADVANCED DATA VERIFICATION	Use advanced statistical and analytical techniques to compare data from multiple cruises, identifying potential inconsistencies, outlier, or systematic biases between datasets.
SYSTEMATIC BIAS IDENTIFICATION AND CORRECTION	Identify systematic biases that arise when merging independent datasets. Depending on the approach taken, QC2 may either document these biases for transparency or apply corrections based on established methodologies (e.g., reference datasets, climatologies, crossover analyses).
UNCERTAINTY ASSESSMENT	Quantify uncertainty across datasets to provide users with confidence levels for different measurements. This step ensures that data users understand the limitations and reliability of merged datasets.
DETAILED DOCUMENTATION	Document all QC2 procedures, including how biases were identified and whether they were corrected. This documentation does not alter original cruise reports but is essential for ensuring traceability and transparency in final data products.
CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT	Regularly review and refine QC2 methodologies, integrating advancements in statistical techniques, reference datasets, and best practices from global data initiatives (e.g., GLODAP).

Box 2: Framework for uncertainty estimates (from D2.4 “Report on framework for uncertainty estimates as part of secondary quality control”)

Motivation and background:

- To define a framework to improve the uncertainty estimate of data synthesis products that merge data with different initial uncertainties.
- To provide a more objective and coherent quantification of the final product uncertainty, thereby increasing its usability.
- The framework builds on procedures used in the Global Ocean Data Analysis Project (GLODAP), refining them to enhance the accuracy and reliability of oceanographic data.

Current challenges:

- When combining independent datasets, systematic biases may appear, affecting the accuracy of the final data product.
- Merging data from different sources with varying initial uncertainties poses significant challenges in maintaining data integrity.

Methodology:

- Noise is introduced to both physical and chemical variables.
- Different weighting schemes are compared to calculate systematic biases and final corrections.
- The framework is demonstrated using case studies that incorporate metrology concepts to ensure the comparability of measurement results over time and space.

Key Findings:

- Introducing uniform random noise with moderate to high values does not significantly affect the final QC2 mean offset results but increases the standard deviation.
- A more likely distribution of noise in oceanographic data is a Gaussian distribution with different magnitudes according to the QC/QA reported in the individual data.
- Checking the standard deviation and skewness of residual values helps quantify the coherence and repeatability of a set of cruises.
- Adjustment limits to be defined based on a minimum uncertainty value for high-quality measurements, considering individual uncertainties of each data set.

Recommendations:

- Implement a Monte Carlo approach to introduce random uncertainty in cruise data and assess its effect on QC2 crossover analysis results.
- Foster dialogue between the oceanographic and metrology communities to improve statistical metrology methods for oceanographic data products, ensuring robust QA/QC procedures in the context of data synthesis and QC2.
- Ensure detailed QA/QC information is included in cruise data reports and metadata to quantify precision and accuracy.
- Use persistent identifiers (DOIs or PIDs) to enhance traceability and citation of datasets, aligning with FAIR data principles.

3.5. Maintenance of QC Tools

There is a critical requirement for the development and availability of reliable, well-documented quality control software specifically designed for primary and secondary quality control processes. It is essential to provide updated protocols and instructional materials that guide personnel in the effective use of these tools. These shared resources should include comprehensive training programs that equip users with the necessary skills to implement quality control measures consistently and effectively across all hydrographic activities. The maintenance of QC software tools (QC1 and QC2) is crucial for ensuring the ongoing accuracy and reliability of hydrographic data collected within the future EuroGO-SHIP RI (see D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities” and D2.4 “Report on framework for uncertainty estimates as part of secondary quality control”). Regular maintenance and updates of these tools are necessary to keep pace with evolving standards and technological advancements. Implementing software updates to QC tools incorporates the latest algorithms, error detection techniques, and data processing methods, while upgrading QC software to newer versions offers enhanced features and improved performance. Maintaining comprehensive documentation of QC procedures, calibration records, and validation results ensures transparency and reproducibility. Providing regular training sessions for personnel on the use and maintenance of QC tools ensures they are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge. Continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) automated testing should be implemented to monitor the performance of QC software tools. This ensures that updates and maintenance do not introduce errors, break functionality, or generate incorrect results. Establishing protocols for detecting, troubleshooting, and resolving software issues promptly helps minimize any impact on data quality. Engaging with experts in the field of hydrography and metrology will help stay updated on best practices and emerging technologies, while participating in peer review processes validates QC methodologies and ensures adherence to international standards.

3.6. Data curation and ownership

Effective data curation is not only about managing and storing data but also involves establishing a clear ownership structure that delineates the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders in the management and sharing of hydrographic data. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will implement a framework that ensures transparency, accountability, and

accessibility in data curation processes. In particular, the ownership of data collected under the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will be shared among various stakeholders, including research institutions, individual researchers, and funding agencies. Institutions will be responsible for the initial collection, processing, and documentation of data, and they will ensure that data is curated according to established best practices and standards. PIs and researchers will play a crucial role in contributing to data quality by adhering to protocols and participating in training programs. They will also be responsible for the accurate documentation of their methodologies and findings. On the other hand, funding bodies will have a stake in the data generated through their support, advocating for open access and proper data sharing practices. They encourage compliance with data management plans that outline how data will be curated and shared post-project. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will establish clear protocols for data sharing that respect the rights of data owners while promoting accessibility for the broader scientific community. These protocols will include guidelines on data citation, usage rights, and the conditions under which data can be shared or reused.

4. Quality and excellence

4.1. Overview

The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will be committed to achieving the highest standards of quality and excellence in hydrographic data collection, management, and utilization. This section outlines the best practices, standard operating procedures, and quality control measures that will be implemented to ensure the integrity, reliability, and usability of the data collected. The general aim of an RI is to provide support to these services and to contribute to robust scientific research and informed decision-making.

The section is structured to cover the following key areas:

- Best Practices (BP) and Standard Operating Procedures (SOP): This section highlights the main findings from D3.1 “Report on best practices and traceability, including gap analysis”, including best practices management for data collection and traceability.
- Endorsement processes: This section details the processes for endorsing methodologies, tools, labs, and data products to ensure they meet the required quality standards.
- Expert groups: This section discusses the role of expert groups in developing and validating best practices, as well as their contributions to the continuous improvement of quality standards.
- Intercomparison exercises: This section describes the need for intercomparison exercises to be organized in the framework of a future EuroGO-SHIP RI (see D3.2 “Report on pilot activities relevant to shared facilities”).
- Training programs: This section outlines the training programs designed to equip personnel with the necessary skills and knowledge to implement best practices and maintain high-quality standards.

- (Certified) Reference Materials (C-RM): This section discusses the production and use of certified reference materials, their impact on data quality, and the need for a business case for different parameter CRM's in Europe (see D3.3 "Report on updated salinity best practice", D3.4 "Report on carbonate system reference material production", D3.5 "Nutrient pilot activities").
- Capacity building and sharing: This section explores the initiatives for capacity building and sharing of resources, including specialized equipment, and expertise (see D4.2 "Report summarising the results of consultations with regional networks").

4.2. Best Practices and Standard Operating Procedures

Ocean Best Practices (BPs) and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are fundamental to the future EuroGO-SHIP RI, ensuring that hydrographic data collection, management, and utilization are conducted with the highest standards of quality and excellence. These practices and procedures, with some available in the Ocean Best Practice System (OBPS⁴), provide a structured approach to data handling, promoting consistency, transparency, and reproducibility across all activities within the RI. In this way the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will aim to improve and/or develop BPs/SOPs to optimize work processes, enhance data quality, and facilitate collaboration among national, European, and global groups of experts and practitioners. A key resource in this effort is the GO-SHIP Repeat Hydrography Manual (Hydro Manual | GO-SHIP⁵), which provides standardized methodologies for data collection, CTD operations, and analytical methods (e.g., dissolved oxygen, nutrients, and carbon system parameters). Wherever possible, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will adopt and build upon these established best practices rather than duplicating efforts, ensuring consistency with global hydrographic standards.

The identification, development, and validation of BPs and SOPs are critical steps in maintaining the integrity and reliability of hydrographic data. The process begins with the identification of areas where standardized procedures are needed, which may include data collection, quality control, data and metadata standardization, and training activities. This identification is often driven by the recognition of gaps in existing practices or the need for improved methodologies to address specific challenges.

Once the need for a BP or SOP is identified, the development phase involves a collaborative effort among experts and practitioners. This process includes reviewing existing methodologies, incorporating new technologies, and synthesizing current knowledge to create comprehensive and effective procedures. The development of these practices is guided by the principles of transparency and inclusivity, ensuring that all relevant stakeholders can contribute and provide feedback.

Validation is the final step in the process, where the developed practices are tested and refined through practical application. This involves field testing, intercomparison exercises, and peer reviews to ensure that the procedures are robust, reliable, and applicable under

⁴ <https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/ocean-best-practices-systems/repository/>

⁵ <http://www.go-ship.org/HydroMan.html>

various conditions. The validation process also includes continuous monitoring and updates to incorporate new findings and technological advancements, maintaining the relevance and effectiveness of the BPs and SOPs.

Box 3: Best practices and traceability (from D3.1 “Report on best practices and traceability, including gap analysis”)

Motivation and background:

- BPs lay the foundation for the strength of distributed RI by enabling joint operations that are more efficient and generate added value for individual members.
- Collaboration in national, European, and global groups of experts and practitioners optimizes work processes, leading to improved results and lower costs.
- BPs, SOPs, and methodologies are essential for implementing controlled and comprehensible workflows in heterogeneous groups, ensuring transparency and reproducibility.

Current challenges:

- Differences in labs, sensors, reference materials, skill sets, and circumstances can alter the uncertainty of data sets, potentially degrading data quality.
- Without traceable and reproducible uncertainties, it is impossible to derive Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) from observational data.
- Best Practices must provide guidance for processing data under various conditions and have a modular structure to address different scenarios.

Methodology:

- BPs should be developed through a collaborative process involving all actors, either directly or indirectly, to create trusted practices.
- These practices should address areas such as data collection, quality control, standardization of data and metadata, and include training and knowledge transfer activities.
- The process should be open and inclusive, allowing for community review and feedback to ensure comprehensive consideration of existing knowledge.

Key findings:

- BPs promote traceable and transparent uncertainty estimates, global interoperability of observational data, efficiency of processes, data traceability and reproducibility, seamless linkages between data, models, and applications, and training and capacity development.
- The creation and update of BPs should involve groups of experts and an open review process to build trust and ensure adaptation.
- A modular structure for BPs is essential to provide guidance under various conditions and maintain data quality.

Recommendations:

- Implement a governance model with working groups and a central contact person to ensure coordinated and transparent workflows.
- Establish a repository for BPs documents and media, providing open access and persistent identifiers (DOIs) for created documents.
- Collaborate with national metrology offices and EU-wide metrology infrastructure to ensure the traceability chain to Standard International (SI) units, complete uncertainty estimates and maintain high data quality through CRMs availability.

4.3. Endorsement process

Endorsement processes are essential for ensuring that methodologies, tools, and data products meet the required quality standards within the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. Rather than developing new procedures from scratch, EuroGO-SHIP will build upon and enhance the existing GO-SHIP Repeat Hydrography Manual to ensure alignment with well-established international standards. Recent results from advocated EU projects (MINKE, SapHTies, GEORGE) along with IAPSO Best Practices working groups will be incorporated.

These processes involve a thorough review and validation of practices by a panel of experts (the “Expert Groups”, see next section), who assess the methodologies against predefined criteria. The endorsement process begins with the submission of a practice or tool for review, followed by an evaluation of its effectiveness, reliability, and compliance with international standards. This evaluation includes peer reviews, field testing, and intercomparison exercises to verify the accuracy and applicability of the practice. Once a practice is endorsed, it is documented and made available to the broader scientific community, ensuring that it can be widely adopted and implemented. Additionally, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will seek OBPS endorsement for newly developed best practices, ensuring they are recognized and integrated within the global ocean observing community. Aligning with OBPS will not only enhance credibility and reliability but also foster trust and collaboration among researchers and institutions worldwide.

4.4. Expert groups

The Expert Groups to be established with the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will play a crucial role in the development and validation of Best Practices and SOPs within the EuroGO-SHIP project, as well as in the detailed planning of intercomparison exercises. These groups consist of experts about specific parameters or aspects of the Data Life Cycle, who collaborate to synthesize existing knowledge, identify gaps, and develop new methodologies. The convergence process involves regular meetings, workshops, and consultations where experts share their insights and experiences, leading to the creation of comprehensive and effective practices. Additionally, the Expert Groups will be instrumental in planning and executing intercomparison exercises, which are essential for verifying the accuracy and applicability of methodologies across different contexts. Expert groups also engage in continuous review and refinement of these practices, incorporating feedback from the broader scientific community. This ensures that the future EuroGO-SHIP RI related activities will remain at the forefront of scientific innovation and maintains the highest standards of quality and excellence. More details and recommendations about those groups are contained in D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities”.

4.5. Intercomparison exercises

Intercomparison exercises are a critical component of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI quality assurance framework. These exercises will involve comparing data and methodologies from different sources/groups to identify discrepancies, validate results, and ensure consistency across datasets and labs. Intercomparison exercises will be planned by the expert groups and executed regularly, involving multiple institutions and researchers, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange. The process may include the collection of data under controlled conditions or proficiency tests over blind homogeneous and stable consigned samples, as well as a detailed analysis and comparison of the results. Any discrepancies identified are investigated, and corrective actions are taken to address the underlying issues. By organizing

regular intercomparison exercises among its members, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI ensures that its data is accurate, reliable, and consistent, supporting high-quality scientific research.

4.6. Training programs

During consultation with regional networks (see D4.2 “Report summarising the results of consultations with regional networks”) a strong need for comprehensive and dedicated training programs emerged. Thus, training programs will be a vital component of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI, ensuring that personnel are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to implement best practices and maintain high-quality standards. These programs will be designed to address various aspects of hydrographic data collection, management, and utilization, providing comprehensive training on both fundamental and advanced methodologies. To enhance accessibility and flexibility, the RI will offer a combination of in-person training, at-sea sessions, and e-learning modules, ensuring that a wider audience can benefit from the training opportunities.

The training strategy includes organizing at least one or two training courses per year, selected from proposals submitted by expert groups. These courses will cover essential topics such as research cruise administration and preparation; CTD calibration, use, maintenance and post-processing; LADCP and ship ADCP operations and data processing; Winkler dissolved oxygen measurement and sensor correction; salinity analysis and sensor correction; dissolved inorganic nutrient analysis; transient tracer measurements; analysis of carbonate chemistry parameters (pH, total alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon), and parameter-specific intercomparison exercises. In addition to in-person courses, some of these topics will be covered through e-learning modules, allowing participants to access training remotely and at their own pace.

In addition to these fundamental courses, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will also offer one advanced training course per year, focusing on specialized topics such as data flow, data curation, real time CTD data transmission, or the production and use of secondary standards instead of (or along with) costly certified reference materials (CRM).

At sea training sessions will be organized, potentially via calls to be issued by the future EuroGO-SHIP RI, to provide hands-on experience and practical knowledge in real-world settings.

Some of the training sessions could also be scheduled during major conferences such as the European Geosciences Union (EGU) meetings, facilitating broader participation and knowledge exchange. To further extend the reach of these sessions, recorded lectures and supplementary e-learning materials may be made available online.

Key questions that will be addressed during the planning of these training programs include assessing the current situation on training, which has traditionally been conducted at the institutional level by the previous generation of experts. The number of participants will vary depending on the specific expert groups organizing the training. While the training will be primarily intended for RI members, non-members might be allowed to participate by paying registration fees. This approach ensures inclusivity while maintaining the value of being a

member of the RI. By centralizing and standardizing training, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI can achieve better cost-effectiveness compared to individual countries conducting their own training programs. This centralized approach also facilitates the development and dissemination of common best practices, leading to improved data quality and consistency. To scale the size of the funding required for such an RI, we propose the following example for the training program:

Type of course	Course duration and frequency	Participant numbers	Total estimated Cost
Fundamental training course	2-day workshop, held once per year for each parameter	up to 30 participants	€1,500 x 2 days x 2 instructors + €500 x 30 participants + €7,000 + €1,000 x 30 participants = €58,000 per course
Advanced training course	3-day workshop, held once per year	up to 30 participants	€1,500 x 3 days x 2 instructors + €500 x 30 participants + €7,000 + €1,000 x 30 participants = €61,000 per course
On-board training sessions (excl. ship time)	Call issued once a year for 1 cruise	5 participants per session/ cruise	€2,000 + €1,000 x 5 participants = €7,000 per session
Unit Training Costs			
Instructor fees	€1,500 per day per instructor, with two instructors per course		
Materials and resources	€500 per participant for course materials, equipment, and resources		
Venue and logistics	€7,000 per course for venue rental, catering, and logistics		
Travel and accommodation	€1,000 per participant for travel and accommodation expenses		

By implementing these comprehensive training programs, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI ensures that its current and future personnel are well-prepared to uphold the highest standards of quality and excellence in hydrographic data collection and management, supporting robust scientific research and informed decision-making. The detailed cost estimates provide a clear understanding of the funding required to support these essential training activities.

4.7. Certified Reference Materials (CRM)

Certified Reference Materials (CRM) are essential for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of hydrographic data, particularly for carbon measurements and nutrient analysis (see D3.4 “Report on carbonate system reference material production” and D3.5 “Nutrient pilot activities”). Certification can be achieved by following ISO17034 and that often is not possible for marine observations. For example, the IAPSO Standard Seawater that is used for calibrating salinometers (see D3.3 “Report on updated salinity best practices”) used by the ocean community as a reference material (RM) but only with the intention to achieve comparability of data.

The use of CRMs has a significant impact on the quality of hydrographic data. By providing a standardized reference, CRMs enable primary quality control to be executed and in turn also allow estimating the accuracy of the data. In addition to the accuracy, other procedures need to be applied to also determine the precision while considering both how an uncertainty might be derived, and which is the quantity of interest when later using the observational

data. Because of the difficulties in following ISO17034 a measure of heterogeneity can be estimated by executing analysis of samples following similar procedures and RM across different laboratories and research institutions. This consistency is crucial for estimating the degree of comparability of data from different sources and for integrating datasets into larger, comprehensive analyses.

The production of certified and working RMs involves the careful preparation of materials with known properties and concentrations. This includes stability and homogeneity testing and inter-laboratory comparisons to ensure consistency. Certification, however, is a separate process carried out by a metrology laboratory, where values are determined using primary standards or independent methods to establish SI traceability. Once certified, these materials serve as benchmarks for calibrating instruments and validating analytical methods, ensuring high-quality and comparable oceanographic measurements.

Given that CRMs are currently prepared and sold mostly from outside Europe, often using waters that do not originate from European seas and may have different biogeochemical characteristics, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will establish a business plan for the production and distribution of CRMs within Europe using water from European regional seas. This initiative aims to make these materials more accessible and relevant for European hydrographers compared to what is presently offered. The business plan for producing CRMs in Europe may include some of these key components:

- Market analysis: assess the current demand for CRMs within the European hydrographic community; identify potential users, including research institutions, universities, and environmental monitoring agencies; evaluate the limitations and challenges of the current supply chain, including costs, availability, and biogeochemical relevance.
- Production infrastructure: using knowledge and experience gained from current producers, establish production facilities within Europe, leveraging existing laboratories and expertise and creating links with national metrology institutions; ensure the availability of clean, oligotrophic seawater from European seas to produce CRMs that are biogeochemically relevant to the region; develop and implement rigorous certification processes to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the CRMs, in strict connection to national metrology institutions.
- Cost analysis and pricing strategy: conduct a detailed cost analysis, including the expenses associated with seawater collection, filtration, sterilization, bottling, and distribution; develop a pricing strategy that balances affordability for users with the sustainability of the production process; explore funding opportunities and partnerships to support the initial setup and ongoing operations.

Even if these components are preferred, the alternative of producing and using in-house RM (often called secondary standards) will be further investigated. Especially for marine carbon measurements, this might be a more suitable way in the near future. In-house RM can be produced locally and compared to existing CRM or even send out to primary certification laboratories inside and outside Europe. Such a model will increase the availability of RM and ensure high-quality carbon data until a European facility is found to set up carbon CRM production in Europe. These plans are continuously discussed in the framework of the global

marine carbon community to ensure comparable data throughout the global community. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will try to establish distributed facilities for the production and use of secondary standards or in-house RM, with the aim to enhance the availability and use of RM, supporting high-quality data collection and analysis. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will organize training programs on how to best use CRMs and, alternatively, how to produce and use in-house RM.

4.8. Capacity building and sharing

4.8.1. Shared facilities

The effective utilization of shared facilities is crucial for enhancing the capabilities of the hydrographic community within the future EuroGO-SHIP RI (see D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities” and D3.2 “Report on pilot activities relevant to shared facilities”).

As the scientific community increasingly recognizes the importance of high-quality data for research and policy-making (see D4.1 “Report summarising the science case for a future EuroGO-SHIP RI”), the demand for shared facilities has grown significantly. Researchers often face challenges in accessing specialized equipment and resources necessary for hydrographic studies. Rather than focusing on the direct exchange of specialized instruments, shared facilities within the EuroGO-SHIP RI will primarily involve:

- Inviting external research groups to participate in cruises with their own equipment, facilitating collaborative data collection while optimizing ship time and resources.
- Providing access to shore-based laboratories for sample analysis, allowing researchers to send samples to specialized and accredited facilities equipped with high-precision instruments and trained technicians.
- Sharing specific laboratory instruments where feasible, such as salinometers, LADCPs, and Winkler titration systems for oxygen analysis, enabling broader access to high-quality data processing capabilities.
- Access to advanced equipment: Many research institutions may lack the funding or resources to acquire state-of-the-art instruments.

These shared resources will support a more integrated and efficient approach to hydrographic research, ensuring consistency in data quality while maximizing the impact of available facilities. By pooling resources, institutions can reduce operational costs associated with maintaining and upgrading equipment. Shared facilities allow for the efficient allocation of funding, ensuring that resources are used effectively across multiple projects. Additionally, shared facilities foster collaboration among researchers from different institutions, promoting knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary approaches to scientific challenges.

To ensure that shared facilities are utilized effectively, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will implement several strategies:

1. Centralized information platform (see next section): Develop a centralized platform where researchers can access information about available shared facilities, including equipment specifications, availability, and procedures.

2. Demand assessment: Conduct regular assessments of the demand for specific facilities and equipment.
3. Collaborative research initiatives: Encourage collaborative research initiatives that leverage shared facilities, by promoting joint projects.
4. Feedback: Establish feedback mechanisms to gather input from users regarding their experiences with shared facilities and the platform.

4.8.2. EuroGO-HUB: a centralized information platform

Capacity building and sharing within the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will be aimed at enhancing the capabilities of the hydrographic community and ensuring the efficient use of resources. The development of a centralized information platform – the “EuroGO-HUB” – aims at facilitating the sharing of equipment and capacities and will be a key component of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI's capacity building and sharing strategy. This platform will provide a “catalogue of hydrographic expertise”, a forum, and a repository of information on e.g. reference materials, best practices, training courses, e-learning resources and workshops, specialized equipment, and other shared facilities. It will also facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange among researchers and institutions.

EuroGO-HUB will include information on the expertise of institutions and research groups in Europe. This information will help researchers identify potential partners and collaborators for the co-designing of research cruises, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange. The platform will also provide information on planned research cruises and opportunities for equipment sharing. This information will help researchers coordinate their activities and make efficient use of available resources. It will be possible to collect and access information on the demand for shared facilities, helping to ensure that these facilities are used efficiently and effectively. The platform will facilitate various forms of collaboration and resource sharing, including barter arrangements, scientific collaboration, Transnational Access (TNA), an owned equipment pool, and capacity sharing.

Additionally, EuroGO-HUB will feature a forum where communities associated with each expert group can seek technical advice. This forum will enable users to ask questions, share experiences, and receive guidance from their peers and experts, fostering a collaborative and supportive environment.

5. Community engagement

5.1. Overview

The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will implement a comprehensive community engagement strategy that includes the development of a centralized platform/forum (as described above), effective communication strategies, the establishment of expert groups dedicated to specific parameters and procedures, and the organization of science meetings. These initiatives will facilitate collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the sharing of resources, ultimately contributing to the goals of delivering high-quality, reliable, and interoperable hydrographic

data, optimizing funding opportunities. More details on the needs expressed by various stakeholders are available in D4.2 “Report summarising the results of consultations with regional networks”, D4.3 “Report on the results of consultations government ministries and funding agencies” and D4.4 “Report summarising the results of consultations with end users”.

5.2. Centralized platform/forum

The centralized platform, EuroGO-HUB, described above, will be a key component of the community engagement strategy. This platform will provide a space for researchers and institutions to connect, share expertise, and collaborate on various projects.

EuroGO-HUB contribution to community engagement	
Catalogue of expertise	EuroGO-HUB will include a comprehensive catalogue of expertise, detailing the skills and knowledge of institutions and research groups across Europe. This catalogue will help researchers identify potential partners and collaborators, fostering scientific collaborations and enhancing the overall capabilities of the hydrographic community.
Scientific collaborations	The platform will facilitate the initiation and coordination of scientific collaborations. By providing information on planned research cruises and opportunities for equipment sharing, EuroGO-HUB will help researchers coordinate their activities and make efficient use of available resources.
Community forum	EuroGO-HUB will feature a forum where communities associated with each expert group can seek technical advice. This forum will enable users to ask specialized questions, share experiences, and receive guidance from their peers and experts, fostering a collaborative and supportive environment.
Free berths and TNA opportunities	The platform will also advertise free berths and Transnational Access (TNA) opportunities, helping researchers to participate in research cruises and access specialized facilities. This will enhance the accessibility of resources and support the development of high-quality hydrographic data.
Opportunities for Early Career Scientists (ECS)	EuroGO-HUB will promote opportunities for ECS, including mentorship programs, training workshops, networking events, and participation in research cruises. By doing so the platform will support the next generation of hydrographic researchers and enhance knowledge transfer within the community.

5.3. Expert groups

Expert groups (see also section 4.4 and D2.2 “Report of refined scope of shared facilities”) will play a crucial role in the future EuroGO-SHIP RI, providing specialized knowledge and guidance on various aspects of hydrography. Each expert group will have clear terms of reference, outlining their rationale, impacts, specific objectives, and *modus operandi*. These terms of reference will ensure the groups are focused and effective in their contributions to the project, and for each specific parameter, to develop and validate best practices, organize intercomparison exercises, and ensure high standards of data quality and reliability.

In addition to the parameter-specific expert group, the future RI will establish an expert group focused on data and products. This group will oversee the production of guidelines to hydrographers on data submission steps and data flow.

5.4. Science meetings

Science meetings will be organized annually to facilitate knowledge exchange, networking, and capacity building within the hydrographic community. These meetings will feature flexible agendas that include scientific discussions, training activities, and stakeholder engagement sessions. In addition, they will provide a platform for researchers to share their findings, discuss challenges, and explore new opportunities for collaboration. The agendas for the annual meetings will be flexible, allowing for a wide range of topics to be covered and ensuring that the meetings are relevant and valuable to all participants. The funding structure for these meetings will be designed to ensure accessibility: while the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will cover the organization costs, participants will be responsible for their travel and accommodation expenses. Training activities will be an integral part of the science meetings, providing researchers with the skills and knowledge they need to effectively use reference materials, specialized equipment, and best practices in hydrography. The RI will engage with regional networks, such as ICES and MONGOOS, to ensure that the needs and perspectives of different regions are considered and addressed. This engagement will help to build a more inclusive and comprehensive hydrographic community (see D4.2 “Report summarising the results of consultations with regional networks”). The meetings will also serve as a means to engage with stakeholders, including data users, to ensure that the hydrographic data produced by the project meets their needs and supports their research and decision-making processes (see and D4.4 “Report summarising the results of consultations with end users”). This engagement will help to ensure the relevance and impact of the project's outputs. Effective communication is essential for engaging the hydrographic community and ensuring the success of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. The project will implement various communication strategies to reach out to hydrographers and related stakeholders. The RI will actively reach out to hydrographers who are not yet involved, expanding the community and fostering greater collaboration. This outreach will include targeted communications, promotional materials, and engagement through professional networks and conferences.

6. Administration and leadership

6.1. Overview

This section outlines the administrative and leadership structures necessary for the successful transition and operation of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. It covers strategies for advocacy and communication, leadership and management, and the governance structure that will support the RI's objectives. These points will be addressed more in detail by the Deliverable D5.2. “Summary of the range of possible RI structures, with preferred option” due at the end of the project.

6.2. Advocacy and communication

Effective advocacy and communication are essential for raising awareness about the future EuroGO-SHIP RI and securing support from stakeholders.

6.2.1. Advocacy for hydrography

Effective advocacy for hydrography is crucial to raising awareness about its significance in marine research and environmental management. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will implement targeted advocacy strategies aimed at engaging policymakers, funding agencies, and stakeholders to highlight the essential role of hydrographic data in supporting sustainable development and informed decision-making. This advocacy will include the dissemination of compelling case studies that demonstrate the impact of high-quality hydrographic research on marine conservation, climate change monitoring, resource management, ocean and weather forecasting. Fostering partnerships with relevant organizations and participating in key conferences and workshops, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will work to ensure that hydrography is recognized as a vital component of the broader scientific community. Through these efforts, the RI aims to secure necessary funding and support, ultimately enhancing the capacity for high-quality hydrographic research and data management across Europe.

6.2.2. Stakeholder engagement

Developing a comprehensive stakeholder engagement plan is crucial for identifying and involving key stakeholders, including government agencies, research institutions, industry partners, and the public. The plan should include the identification and categorization of stakeholders based on their influence, interest, and potential contributions to the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. The engagement strategies need to be tailored to the different stakeholder groups, ensuring that their specific needs and interests are addressed.

6.2.3. Communication channels

Utilizing a variety of communication channels will help disseminate information about the RI's activities and achievements effectively. Key channels include social media to share updates, success stories, and upcoming events. The RI will publish regular newsletters to provide in-depth updates on the RI's progress, highlight key achievements, and share relevant news and opportunities. The future EuroGO-SHIP RI aims at organizing webinars and workshops to engage with stakeholders, provide training, and facilitate knowledge exchange. Additionally, the RI will participate in and host conferences and events to showcase the RI's work, network with stakeholders, and foster collaborations.

6.2.4. Public relations

Implementing public relations campaigns will help highlight the importance of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI and its contributions to marine science and environmental monitoring. These activities will include issuing press releases to announce major milestones, ongoing and

upcoming oceanographic cruises, new partnerships, and significant achievements, building relationships with journalists and media outlets to secure coverage of the RI's activities and impact, launching public awareness campaigns to educate the broader community about the RI's mission and the importance of oceanographic research.

6.2.5. Key messages

Crafting clear key messages is essential for effective communication. Focus will be on the following themes:

- Mission and vision: Clearly articulate the mission and vision of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI to inspire and engage stakeholders.
- Impact and benefits: Emphasize the impact and benefits of the RI, including its contributions to scientific research, environmental sustainability, ocean and weather forecasting, and policy development.
- Success stories: Share success stories and case studies that demonstrate the RI's achievements and the value of its data and services.

6.3. Leadership and management

Strong leadership and effective management are essential for the successful operation of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. The leadership structure of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will be designed to provide clear direction, foster collaboration, and ensure accountability and would include:

- Governing board to provide strategic direction, oversee the RI's activities, and ensure alignment with its mission and objectives.
- Executive committee to oversee operational planning, resource allocation, and performance monitoring.
- Advisory panels to ensure that the RI's activities are informed by the latest scientific knowledge and best practices.

Detailed operational plans will be developed and implemented that outline the RI's activities, timelines, and resource requirements. It is of primary importance that efficient allocation of resources is ensured, including funding, personnel, and equipment, to support the RI's activities. This will be achieved by prioritizing projects and initiatives that align with the RI's strategic objectives. A performance monitoring system that resembles those recommended by ESFRI for its RIs, will be put in place to track progress against key performance indicators (KPIs) and to ensure that the RI's activities are on track.

Investing in leadership development is also essential for building a strong and effective leadership team. This can be done by providing ongoing training and development opportunities for current and emerging leaders within the RI (leadership training, management skills development, and opportunities for professional growth). Also, a mentorship and coaching program would be a way to support the development of leadership skills and provide guidance to emerging leaders. One key aspect is also the development and implementation of succession planning strategies to ensure continuity of leadership within the RI (e.g., identifying potential future leaders and providing them with the training and development opportunities needed to prepare them for leadership roles).

6.4. Transition from project to RI

The transition from a project-based approach to a sustainable RI for the EuroGO-SHIP project requires careful planning and execution. Securing long-term funding is a critical first step, involving the identification and acquisition of financial support from various sources such as national and international funding agencies, member institutions, participation to European projects as a legal entity, and industry partnerships.

Establishing robust governance structures is essential for providing strategic direction and oversight. As outlined above, a governing board, composed of representatives from key stakeholder groups, will be formed to guide the RI's activities. An executive committee, including the RI Director, Deputy Director, and heads of key operational units, will manage day-to-day operations, while advisory panels of experts will offer guidance on scientific, technical, and policy matters.

Ensuring continuity of operations involves operational plans that will regularly be reviewed and updated to reflect changing priorities and emerging opportunities. Resources, including funding, personnel, and equipment, will be allocated efficiently to support the RI's activities, with a focus on projects that align with strategic objectives. Performance monitoring systems will track progress against KPIs to ensure activities remain on track.

Building institutional and international capacity is another crucial aspect of the transition. Ongoing training and development opportunities will be provided to staff, enhancing their skills and knowledge to support the RI's operations. Knowledge transfer mechanisms, such as documentation of procedures, mentoring programs, and collaborative projects, will ensure expertise and best practices are shared across the RI. Engaging with member institutions and stakeholders will further build capacity and support the RI's activities.

A Science Plan for the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will outline the research priorities and objectives that will guide the RI's activities. This plan will be developed in consultation with stakeholders and experts to ensure it addresses the most pressing scientific challenges and opportunities in oceanographic research. Key components of the Science Plan include identifying priority research areas, such as climate change, ocean and weather forecasting, marine biodiversity, and ocean health, and outlining specific research projects and initiatives that will be undertaken. The plan will also detail the methodologies and technologies to be employed, as well as the expected outcomes and impacts of the research. Regular reviews and updates of the Science Plan will ensure it remains relevant and responsive to emerging scientific needs and advancements.

6.5. Collaboration and synergies with other RIs

During the RI engagement workshop that EuroGO-SHIP organized in June 2024 (see D5.1 “Summary of RI requirements and potential help that they can give to the new RI under what circumstances”), it emerged that the openness of marine-related RIs in Europe to collaborate with EuroGO-SHIP presents significant opportunities for enhancing efficiency and resource sharing across the scientific community. As marine-related RIs work together, they can create a more integrated and cohesive research environment, ultimately advancing the

understanding of marine ecosystems and addressing pressing environmental challenges more effectively. Marine RIs across Europe have expressed a strong interest in partnering with EuroGO-SHIP, particularly in key areas such as best practices, training, data curation, and pan-European cooperation. These partnerships are vital for fostering a unified approach to oceanographic research, as they enable the sharing of knowledge and resources that can significantly enhance the overall effectiveness of the EuroGO-SHIP initiative. By collaborating with various RIs, EuroGO-SHIP can leverage established methodologies and training programs, ensuring that researchers are equipped with the latest skills and tools necessary for high-quality data management and analysis. For instance, establishing partnerships with initiatives such as Eurofleets, the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS), and EuroArgo can enhance synergies. Collaborating with Eurofleets, which focuses on providing access to research vessels and marine equipment, would significantly enhance the operational capabilities of a future EuroGO-SHIP RI. Joint initiatives could include coordinated research cruises, and collaborative training programs for researchers. Such partnerships would not only optimize resource utilization but also expand the scope of scientific investigations across European waters. Partnering with OBPS presents an opportunity to align future EuroGO-SHIP RI's methodologies with globally recognized best practices in oceanographic research. This collaboration could involve the endorsement by the future EuroGO-SHIP RI to hydrographic related protocols. Additionally, sharing knowledge and resources with OBPS would facilitate the dissemination of best practices among the hydrographic community. Forming a strong partnership with the EuroArgo ERIC would be very beneficial to both parties, facilitating an increase in the number of Argo float cross calibrations at sea while the EuroGO-SHIP partners would gain a lot of knowledge from the expertise developed by the EuroArgo ERIC over the last decade. To formalize these collaborations, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will pursue the establishment of Memoranda of Understanding (MoU) with partner infrastructures. These MoU's will outline the objectives, responsibilities, and expected outcomes of the collaborations, providing a clear framework for cooperation.

7. Mapping EuroGO-SHIP to ESFRI Objectives

The future EuroGO-SHIP RI is designed to align with the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) objectives, ensuring it meets the highest standards of scientific excellence and operational efficiency. This section maps the future EuroGO-SHIP RI to the nine ESFRI objectives, demonstrating how it will be developed to become a leading research infrastructure.

Enabling scientific excellence: future EuroGO-SHIP RI is committed to enabling scientific excellence by providing high-quality (and of known quality), reliable data. The RI will ensure that researchers have access to the best tools and resources to advance scientific knowledge and address critical challenges.

Delivery of education and training: The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will deliver comprehensive education and training programs to build capacity and enhance the skills of researchers and practitioners. These programs will include workshops, webinars, on-board training sessions,

and advanced courses, ensuring that personnel are equipped with the necessary knowledge and expertise to conduct high-quality research and data management.

Enhancing transnational collaboration in Europe: future EuroGO-SHIP RI will enhance transnational collaboration by fostering partnerships and cooperation among national, European, and global research institutions. The RI will provide a centralized platform for collaborative research, promoting interdisciplinary studies and knowledge exchange across borders.

Facilitating economic activity: future EuroGO-SHIP RI will facilitate economic activity in sectors such as maritime industry, tourism, fisheries, environmental monitoring, ocean and weather forecasting and sustainable resource management.

Outreach to the public: future EuroGO-SHIP RI will be dedicated to outreach and public engagement, raising awareness about the importance of oceanographic research and its impact on environmental sustainability. The RI will implement public awareness campaigns, organize engagement activities, and provide accessible information to the broader community.

Optimising data use: The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will optimize data use by implementing best practices in data management, curation, and quality control. The RI will ensure that data is collected, stored, and shared in standardized formats, facilitating easy access and integration.

Provision of scientific advice: future EuroGO-SHIP RI will provide scientific advice to policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the broader scientific community. The RI will leverage its expertise and high-quality data to inform policy development, environmental management, and regulatory decisions, contributing to evidence-based decision-making and sustainable practices.

Facilitating international cooperation: future EuroGO-SHIP RI will facilitate international cooperation by participating in global initiatives and networks, such as the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Argo program. The RI will engage with international partners to share data, knowledge, and best practices, promoting global collaboration and addressing shared environmental challenges.

Optimising management: The future EuroGO-SHIP RI will implement robust management practices to ensure efficient and effective operations. This includes establishing clear governance structures, developing detailed operational plans, and implementing performance monitoring systems.

Table 1. Matrix providing a comprehensive overview of how EuroGO-SHIP services align with the ESFRI objectives.

ESFRI Objectives Euro GO-SHIP services	Enabling scientific excellence	Delivery of education and training	Enhancing transnational collaboration in Europe	Facilitating economic activity	Outreach to the public	Optimising data use	Provision of scientific advice	Facilitating international cooperation	Optimising management
Logistical support for hydrographic cruises (training, guidelines)									
Data acquisition & management									
Training and workshops (BPs, data curation, QC tools, use of (C)RM, etc.)									
QC tools, intercomparison exercises									
Endorsement of BP and SOPs recommended for hydrography									
Development of new SOPs for data access and sharing (data flow, use of QC tools)									
Expert consultation (Forum, Expert Groups)									
Collaboration and networking platform									
Recommended version control system for data									
Community engagement initiatives (on-board training, TNA, berth availability, etc.)									
Capacity building and knowledge transfer programs									

8. Conclusion

The future EuroGO-SHIP RI is poised to become a cornerstone of oceanographic research, providing high-quality data, fostering collaboration, and supporting innovative methodologies and technologies.

We acknowledge that some services proposed for the future EuroGO-SHIP RI are already available, either through other RIs, albeit in a marginal capacity, or within the private sector, such as the provision of Certified Reference Materials (CRMs). However, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI is uniquely positioned to fill critical gaps in these existing services by enhancing and tailoring them specifically for the hydrographic community. By focusing on the unique needs and challenges faced by hydrographic researchers, EuroGO-SHIP can refine these services to ensure they are more effective, accessible, and relevant (see tables in Appendix 1 on more details on how the future EuroGO-SHIP might fill those gaps). This approach will improve the quality and applicability of the services offered. The creation of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will represent a significant opportunity for the hydrographic community. Without this infrastructure, the community misses out on several critical services and benefits. Firstly, the lack of a coordinated infrastructure leads to fragmented efforts in data collection and analysis. Individual research institutions may continue to operate in isolation, resulting in inconsistencies in methodologies and data quality. This fragmentation hinders the ability to produce reliable and comparable datasets, ultimately impacting the validity of scientific findings and their applicability to policy-making. Secondly, the absence of EuroGO-SHIP RI limits opportunities for capacity building and training within the hydrographic community. Without comprehensive training programs and shared resources, researchers and technicians struggle to develop the necessary skills and knowledge to conduct high-quality hydrography. Moreover, the absence or only fragmented use of rigorous quality control tools and best practices results in lower than optimal data quality, impacting the reliability and usability of hydrographic data for scientific research and policy development. Without a centralized platform for collaboration, researchers face challenges in coordinating efforts, sharing knowledge, and leveraging collective expertise, hindering the advancement of oceanographic research.

In conclusion, the establishment of the future EuroGO-SHIP RI is essential for advancing oceanographic research, fostering collaboration, and supporting the hydrographic community. By aligning with the ESFRI objectives and providing critical services, the future EuroGO-SHIP RI will play a pivotal role in enhancing scientific excellence and addressing global environmental challenges.

Appendix 1 – List of relevant project deliverables

D2.2	Report of refined scope of shared facilities
D2.3	Report of data curation recommendations including gap analysis
D2.4	Report on framework for uncertainty estimates as part of secondary quality control
D3.1	Report on best practices and traceability, including gap analysis
D3.2	Report on pilot activities relevant to shared facilities
D3.3	Report on updated salinity best practice
D3.4	Report on carbonate system reference material production
D3.5	Nutrient pilot activities
D4.1	Report summarising the science case for a future EuroGO-SHIP RI
D4.2	Report summarising the results of consultations with regional networks
D4.3	Report on the results of consultations government ministries and funding agencies
D4.4	Report summarising the results of consultations with end users
D5.1	Summary of RI requirements and potential help that they can give to the new RI under what circumstances

Appendix 2 – Potential services provided by the future EuroGO-SHIP RI

The following tables provide an overview of the potential services provided by the future EuroGO-SHIP RI in different areas, compared to existing similar services and the identified need for a dedicated EuroGO-SHIP RI contribution.

Hydrographic cruise planning and execution		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Logistical support	Limited support from individual institutions	Centralized coordination and resource allocation for efficient cruise planning
Data management	Fragmented systems	Integrated data logging, monitoring, and post-cruise processing
Training and workshops	Sporadic training sessions	Regular, standardized training on best practices

Data acquisition		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Provision of instruments	Limited availability from individual institutions	Ensures consistent access to high-quality CTD sensors, Niskin bottles, and ADCPs
Instrument calibration and maintenance	Some calibration facilities available	Consistent access to calibration and maintenance across all cruises
Protocol development	Varies by institution	Standardized protocols ensure consistency and reliability
Training on data acquisition techniques	Sporadic training sessions	Regular, standardized training on the use of CTD sensors, Niskin bottles, and ADCPs
Expert consultation	Ad-hoc advice from experts	Structured consultation and troubleshooting support
Collaboration and networking	Informal networks	Centralized platform for collaboration and sharing
Training and workshops	Sporadic training sessions	Regular, standardized training on best practices
Real-time data transfer for CTD profiles and underway	Varies by nation	Standardised protocols, software and training for ship to shore transfer of CTD profiles and underway data in near-real time.

Data curation		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Standardized data formats	Varies by institution	Ensures consistency and interoperability across datasets.
Comprehensive data documentation	Limited documentation practices	Provides detailed context and ensures reproducibility of data
Version control systems	Ad-hoc version control	Tracks changes and updates, ensuring access to the most current data
Data access and sharing protocols	Fragmented access protocols	Facilitates seamless data sharing and collaboration
Persistent identifiers (Cruise ID/DOIs/PIDs)	Inconsistent use of identifiers	Enhances traceability and citation, aligning with FAIR data principles
Mapping data pathways	Limited mapping exercises	Identifies key points of data transfer and processing, optimizing data integration

Assessment of data handling practices	Varies by NODC	Ensures alignment with future EuroGO-SHIP RI standards and best practices.
Optimization of data integration	Fragmented data integration	Facilitates seamless data sharing and collaboration between different NODCs
Training and workshops	Sporadic training sessions	Regular, standardized training data curation

Maintenance of QC Tools		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Software update and upgrade support	Ad-hoc updates	Provides centralized support for implementing the latest software updates and upgrades.
Comprehensive documentation	Varies by institution	Standardizes documentation practices, ensuring transparency and reproducibility.
Training programs	Sporadic training sessions	Offers regular, standardized training on QC tool usage
Continuous monitoring and troubleshooting	Limited monitoring	Establishes protocols for continuous monitoring and prompt troubleshooting of QC tools
Expert consultation and peer review	Informal networks	Facilitates structured consultation and peer review processes to validate QC methodologies.

Community Engagement		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Centralized community forum	Separate, fragmented communication channels.	Establishment of a centralized platform for stakeholder engagement
Expert group collaborations	Informal expert networks	Formalized expert groups for structured knowledge sharing
Public outreach initiatives	Occasional awareness campaigns	Regular public engagement activities and outreach programs
Mentorship and networking opportunities	Some initiatives exist but they are not hydrography-focused.	A EuroGO-SHIP-specific ECS program to strengthen long-term expertise development

Best Practices and Standard Operating Procedures		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Updated methodologies	GO-SHIP Hydro Manual serves as a key global reference	Updates and additions are needed
Develop and endorse SOPs and Best Practices	OBPS (IOC-UNESCO) provides a repository, but contributions vary in detail and scope	A EuroGO-SHIP-endorsed set of best practices to ensure consistency across European hydrographic activities

Data management and access		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
User-friendly data access tools	Complicated access procedures	Development of user-friendly interfaces for data sharing
Metadata standardization guidelines	Existing metadata practices, but they vary between programs	Establishment of standardized metadata practices for tracking data provenance and enabling cross-program comparisons
Guidelines for data submission and access	SeaDataNet, EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service,	A coordinated approach to integrate hydrographic data seamlessly into

	NODCs offer data repositories but do not fully cover EuroGO-SHIP-specific requirements	European and global data systems while ensuring long-term accessibility
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Training and capacity building		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Comprehensive training modules	Ad-hoc training offerings	Standardized, targeted training modules for hydrographic research
Knowledge transfer programs	Limited mentorship opportunities	Structured mentoring programs to foster skills development
E-learning platforms	Few online resources available. OceanTeacher (IODE) offers training but is broad and not EuroGO-SHIP specific	Development of e-learning platforms for wide access to training
At-sea training opportunities	Some opportunities exist through AQUARIUS, Eurofleets+ and POGO training cruises	Dedicated EuroGO-SHIP training framework to enhance capacity building in hydrography

Certified Reference Materials (CRM)		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Development/distribution of European CRMs	Not available	A dedicated European CRM production pipeline to ensure long-term availability of reference materials
Linking hydrographic and metrology communities	SCOR WG 147 and JCOMMOPS have some initiatives, but integration with hydrography is limited	A structured engagement framework between metrology and hydrography experts
Certification and documentation of CRMs	Some standards exist through ISO and BIPM, but application in oceanography is fragmented.	A clear, standardized protocol for CRM certification in oceanography

Advocacy and leadership		
Potential service provided	Existing service	Need for future EuroGO-SHIP RI
Advocacy for sustained funding and infrastructure support	Some efforts exist through GOOS and Ocean Decade, but EuroGO-SHIP is not yet integrated.	A clear, long-term funding strategy for sustaining European hydrographic activities.
Policy development support	Limited policy guidance available	Comprehensive support for evidence-based policy development
Resource allocation strategies	Disparate resource distribution	Streamlined resource allocation to optimize operational efficiency